

The impact of implementing total quality on the Banking profitability of Saudi market Case study of Al Rajhi Bank

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Abstract

this study aimed to identify the total quality of banking service and its impact on the profitability of Al Rajhi bank represented by return on investment rates, with the goal to make recommendations that will help the bank to improve the quality of banking service provided to customers. The multiple regression models and a T-test were used to examine the hypotheses and produce results for decision makers, through SPSS program. The study reached a number of results, the most important are: the existence of significant statistical relations between the total quality of banking service provided and the satisfaction of customers, between the satisfaction and loyalty of Al Rajhi Bank customers, and the quality of the banking service provided effectively and the profitability of Al Rajhi Bank. The study concluded with a number of recommendations, the most important are: Al Rajhi Bank's quality of service, especially the tangible physical aspects showed the interest and personal knowledge of customers, holding targeted training courses to improve performance and speed of delivery, good treatment of customers, and their impact on customer's satisfaction and degree of loyalty, and linking it to the profitability of the bank
Keywords: Total quality, Al Rajhi bank, customer satisfaction, banking profitability.

1. Introduction

Quality considers an old concept, and it's a genuine concept in our Islamic religion, where quality consist of accuracy and perfection, and total quality consider one of the modern management concepts that based on the collection of important principles and ideas for any institution, where it work continuously to implement it, in order to achieve the best possible performance, improve productivity level, increase profitability, and improve its reputation at the national and international markets, in light of the increase in number of banks. Therefore, it became necessary from it to complete the quality systems, features, and potentials to receive the universal acceptance according to the internationally agreed quality standards, thus, it will be able to walk toward the competition and survive in the economic, political, and social modern twists, under the fierce competition of major international banks, which have all the human, technical, and financial potentials and resources; which are difficult for Saudi banks to face, and continue the fearful competition with it, but it may be faced with implementing the total quality standards and the Islamic banking. Along with the economic crisis that happened to the world in 2006, a major global banks fell that didn't expect this decline and destruction, and for its end to come this way, and in this speed, it's like a type of craziness, and one of the impossible things to achieve, where its huge capital didn't help it to survive.

If we display a quick glance about Al Rajhi bank; in year 1978, the individual institutions were merged under the name Al Rajhi company for exchange and commerce, in the year 1987 transformed into a stock company under the noble Royal decree number (59), and declared Al Rajhi banking company for investment as a Saudi participation holding company under the Ministerial decree number (1398) two years later. Al Rajhi bank considers one of the major banking and investment companies that participate in 100% Saudi capital, where it started with (750) million Saudi riyals, and then the capital doubled to (1500) million Saudi riyals, and then granted contribution and divided the share to reach (2250) million Saudi riyals. The second doubled-up capital of (4500) million Saudi riyals happened a couple of years later, then granted contribution and divided the share to reach (6750) million Saudi riyals, and then came the third doubled-up of capital to become (13500) million Saudi riyals. In 2008, the capital increased to become (15) billion Saudi riyals, and increased again; in 2013 to become (16,250) billion Saudi riyals.

The bank managed through managerial regulation that includes: general management in Riyadh and six regional directorates spread over the following areas: Central, Western, Eastern, Qassim, Hail, Al-Medina, North, and South, and owns the largest bank branches network in the Kingdom with more than 500

branches, exchange centers, and the largest ATM network setting with more than 2000 devices, while the number of distributed POS on dealers and traders amount to more than 17000 locations.

2. Study question

First question: What is the impact of implementing total quality on the profitability of Saudi banking market?

Second question: Are there any statistically significant differences from the standpoint of study sample due to the variables (sex, qualifications)?

3. Study importance

Study importance derived through the challenges that face the Saudi banks in the current era, especially after Saudi Arabia became part of the WTO, which imposes on it to change its ways and methods to provide services and adopt new modern marketing concepts that make it cope with the international banks, which help them to increase customer satisfaction, win new customers, and keep them under fierce competition from the international banks, and also in the shadow of economic and political conditions, whether local or global, and under the threats that surround the region in particular.

4. Study problem

The study problem resides in the recognition of total quality implementation impact on the Saudi banking market, where the most important challenges that face the financial and banking firms is how to have successful and excellence services, in light of increased fierce competition in the market, whether from the local or global banks, and in view of the increased customers' awareness and desire to have multiple, easy, and available banking services; any time and any place that keep up with the rapid growth of modern technologies.

5. Study objectives

- Identify the impact of total quality implementation of the primary services on the profitability of Al Rajhi Bank.
- Identify the impact of total quality implementation of the supplementary services on the profitability of Al Rajhi Bank.

6. Study hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no statistically significant impact of implementing quality on the tangible earnings at Al Rajhi Bank.

H₀₂: There is no statistically significant impact of implementing quality on the intangible earnings at Al Rajhi Bank.

7. Previous studies

The study of (Al-Sern, 2004/2005) titled a new way to study the services quality of banking sector, is a comparative field study that compare between some of the Syrian and Jordanian banks, where the study aimed to display and introduce the intellectual and philosophical framework for the elements of the new method (globalization, quality service, and banking service), considering it as a modern management method to support and strengthen the banks' position, with analyzing the relationships and connections between elements of the new way to improve and develop the quality.

While the pilot study of (Al-Said, 2004) on Algerian banks addressed the impact of TQM implementation on the decision making maturity, where the study aimed to identify the banks' commitment level about implementing the TQM concept, its success level, and the maturity degree of decision made in the banks

that adopted a quality program, and also to determine nature of relationship between decision made maturity and TQM successful implementation.

Study of (Meraj et al., 2005) aimed to identify the recognition level of clients at the operating commercial banks in the (Guardia) area, to the quality of banking services provided to them. The study showed a negative gap between the expectations of commercial banks operating in Algeria to the quality of banking service provided and their recognition of it. Study of (Al-Taleb, 2005) entitled measuring the quality of Islamic banking services in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, where the study aimed to identify the quality of Islamic banking services in the cities of Amman and Irbid, employ the method to select the loans to verify the relationship between quality of Islamic banking services; from the standpoint of client by using the quality dimensions, which include the tangible, dependability, responsiveness, safety, and sympathy, in addition to providing a database to manage the Jordanian Islamic banks to resolve its situations with respect to the quality of services provided by them.

Study of (Al-Athouri et al., 2007) aimed to measure the quality of banking services at the Yemeni banks; from the clients' perspective by using Serve perfect model, and in order to achieve this goal, the researchers used a questionnaire that distributed on (360) customers from five banks. The study found that level of banking service quality provided by the Yemeni banks (traditional and Islamic), and perceived by customers are high Study of (Abdullah, 2009) results showed that strength of relationship between the three indicators of marketing information systems, bank marketing researchers, and marketing strategy used are not up to par, which means there were malfunctions and failures. Study of (Gougandi, 2009) aimed to see the level of banks' high management concern and interest to the total quality orientation and guidelines, the implementation level of TQM concepts in the practice of different human resources management positions at the banks, and the senior management recognition level of its importance, as well as the impact of that on the employees performance quality. The study also aimed to identify the availability level of favorable cultures and values to the introduction of total quality. The study found that whenever the banks don't implement total quality concepts on the practices of human resource management positions related to transfer, promotion, incentives, and salaries negatively affects the quality of employees' performance to the banking service. The researchers recommend that banks should put a well studied and thoughtful strategy to transform to the TQM approach.

But the study of (Al-Daas, 2010) aimed to determine the impact of total quality on improving the financial performance of Jordanian commercial banks, and one of the most important findings of the study was workers recognition of the Jordanian commercial banks to the importance of each dimension of total quality in the improvement of financial performance. The study also showed the existence of significant correlation relationship between each dimension of TQM and the financial performance improvement in the Jordanian commercial banks. While the study of (Jacob, 2011) represented in the strength and direction of the relationship between the service quality and customer satisfaction, the relationship between bank service tangibility and customer satisfaction, and the strength and direction of the relationship between reliability and customer satisfaction, and how to determine the relationship between them. The importance of research resides in providing the practical solutions of banks, in order to improve the quality of their services, gain customers' satisfaction, and help management to improve and develop the quality of their services to strengthen its competitive position.

8. The study methodology and theoretical framework

9.1 The study methodology:

The study methodology and approach forms the main aspect of research, where it's the essential foundation to identify the real interest and benefit of this research, and it's possible to formulate the methodology by identifying the sources for collecting secondary and primary data and pay attention to identifying the study population, in order to influence the study sample of the research. The methodology shows the study tool used to collect data about the represented study sample, and also takes an important step in the methodology,

which is tool sincerity and constancy. The researcher used the analysis methods in the methodology, which could be formulated as follows: Secondary data: financial statements of Al Rajhi bank taking from the Saudi stock trading site. Primary data: researcher depends to collect it on the questionnaires that were distributed on staffs of Al Rajhi bank in the cities of Mecca, Jeddah, and Riyadh.

9.1.1 Study population: The study population consists of all branches' employees of Al Rajhi bank in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

9.1.2 Study sample: the study sample consists of (150) managerial staffs that were selected randomly and (50) questionnaires were distributed on each of the three areas (Mecca, Jeddah, and Riyadh).

9.1.3 Study tool: The questionnaire was used to collect data related to the study, where the Fifth Likert Scale was adopted to evaluate the responses of study members.

9.1.4 Questionnaire design: a questionnaire consists of (15) questions were designed which related to the study topic: "The impact of total quality implementation on the banking profitability of Saudi market (Al Rajhi bank)."

9.1.5 Tool sincerity and constancy of questionnaire:

The questionnaire was introduced to a number of arbitrators from university professors to examine the accuracy level of formulated expressions in it and the alignment degree of it to the study objectives, and reconsider some terms in this questionnaire in light of the proposed adjustments from the arbitrators.

9.1.6 Methods used in the statistical analysis: Multiple regression model and T-test were used to test hypotheses and come out with the results that benefit the decision makers, by relying on the SPSS software to conduct the required statistical analysis processes.

9.1.7 Study limitation: Spatial boundaries/ limitations: represented in Al Rajhi bank branches scattered all over the areas of Mecca, Jeddah, and Riyadh.

10.1.7 Temporal boundaries/ limitations: represented in the year (2018).

9.2 Theoretical framework: All of the modern global challenges, economic, social, cultural, political, legal, natural, and technological caused to force the service organizations in general, and banking organizations to adopt a sensible scientific method to face these threats and challenges, and invest in the effective humanitarian capabilities to launch the operational and sales performance at more efficient and effective flexibility. TQM considers one of the most purposeful managerial aspects that now became more efficient in investing the available information and communication technologies, which consider a distinctive characteristic of the modern human thought data, and this can be seen in the industrial service institutions, organizations, and boards in general. But in the area of banking service, the management of it through the implementation of TQM seek to make qualitative development of work cycle in the banks, to align with the management requirements and updates of consumption sector in the banking market and keep pace with the developments that aimed to achieve excellencies in all operations perform by the banking institution. Total quality means all the joint and completed efforts of all members of the organization at all levels, in accordance with the requirements, objectives, and capabilities of the institution and the surrounding environment, while total quality management (TQM) means in its entirety, system that include a set of an integrated intellectual philosophies, statistical tools, and management processes used to achieve the objectives and raise the level of customer and employee satisfaction alike, through the continuous improvement of institution and the effective participation of all, for the benefit of company and the self development of its employees, and therefore improve quality of life in the society. Jablonski refers to the concept of TQM to be as other management concepts, which concepts and ideas differ about it, according to the scholar or researcher point of view, but this formulated variation in the concepts are almost equal in the meaningful contents, since its structured around the goal that organization want to achieve, which

represented by the consumer through the interaction of all active parties in it. The level of efforts made by the banking institution management and its staffs in the market is the key determinant for the level of provided banking services, from the consumer viewpoint, where the researcher (Jacob, 2011) pointed out in his study about the relationship between the quality implementation and customer satisfaction, and deduced a direct correlation between the provided quality level and the level of customer satisfaction in the market, and this what Al Rajhi bank demonstrate in all of its branches by satisfying customers, through consumers' continuous consumption of those services, in addition to the ongoing intercourse with the financial bank, where such efforts require a high level of competence, starting from the management activities in making the wise decisions, in light of studying the competitive markets, institution capabilities, and consumer need, and in consistent with the future plan and the expected objectives.

The formation of management decisions and its nature directly reflect the job behavior of individuals and department heads in the financial banks, by implementing all the decisions made by management, and this what proved in the study of (Al-Saed, 2004) about the importance of implementing the total quality in the decision making process and streamlined it in the financial banks, and that shows the success of Al Rajhi bank in reaching the best profits by the formulation of marketing decisions regarding the services provided to consumers, and it demonstrates to us that wise, rational, systematic decision leads to highly efficient and effective implementation of activities, which benefit society, consumer, and banking institution. The institution mainly seeks to achieve the physical profits, but how could it achieve the primary goal without achieving market share from sales or profits volume, where banking institutions strive to achieve the greatest returns or profits between institutions, due to the fierce competition it face from the domestic and international banking institutions, which produce the same provided and alternative services from another party in the consumers' market, where the researcher (Al-Daas, 2010) pointed out in his study to the impact level of implementing TQM on improving the financial performance of banking institutions, and this what Al Rajhi bank show by achieving the higher profits, through increase in consumer numbers of this bank. Market share refers to the banking institution sales ratio between the banking institutions, as a whole in the same sector, and sometimes it measured between all sectors to find out the level, position, and standing of the institution among its competitors, where the share ownership by the institution consider one of the parameters used to identify the rank and respect of institution in the market among other competing institutions, as well as its entrepreneurship level based on the sales volume its own in the market. The good market share achieved many tangible profits for the institutions that own these shares, where the researcher (Al-Taleb, 2005) referred in his study to the importance of implementing TQM by reconsidering the services level provided to consumers, which positively affect the institution's objectives (sales and profits), where Al Rajhi bank considers one of the banking institutions that own sales ratio, which may be the highest in the Saudi banking market, according to what we witness from this institution, where it's the most widespread consumer-infested branches, the one with highest sales, and number of salesmen who assume the responsibility of providing banking services for consumers with different nationalities and levels, and in all parts of the Kingdom, where the number of consumers increase at Al Rajhi bank branches depending on the size of sales area, population, bank size, and number of services required by consumers, where this congestion consider as clear and positive indicator which explains that each of Al Rajhi bank branches in Saudi Arabia own the largest proportion of sales and total market share, if we compare it with the other banking institutions and this market share may reach approximately 50% of the total market share at the banking sector in the Kingdom. The market share plays a big role in gaining profits, but the banking institution doesn't only strive to achieve the physical profits, but seek to achieve the moral side too, which can raise the status of the institution in the eyes of consumers and companies, where the market position consider one of the significant issues for the bank, which promotes the mental and professional value of the bank general management, and all its members and staffs, through honoring this brand name, its management, and its members who strive for bank success. Al Rajhi bank marketing position express the rank of this bank management and its abilities to make the appropriate strategic decisions for the market, and this rank also represent the banking institution's owner name, the trade name, and the bank staffs who work with all their energies, efficiencies, skills, and experiences, in order to reach the general objectives and meet the needs and desires of consumers, through creating a strong strategy derived from the overall efforts of

the institution's in implementing the total quality concept, which reflect the intellectual, psychological value of all consumers who use the banking services provide for them, and this what the researcher (GuFandi, 2009) pointed out in his study that senior bank management pay attention to the total quality and its applications, and its impact on the performance of workers, which proved that management decision directly reflect the overall performance of employees at the banking institution, where each time the institution raise its position and rank in the market among the institutions, it will reflect the reputation of institution in the eye of consumers, which prints the positive image in the mind of consumers in general, which institutions can't achieve without having the sufficient qualifications and expertise, and response to the needs of environment, in addition to the machines, equipments, devices, electronics, and the distinct operating systems which capable of implementing the total quality concept on the ground with generosity, mastering, and high level, which could allow the bank to work on TQM and leadership, in a way that align with the targets and goals of consumers, society, and banking institution

9.2.1 Quality importance: The quality importance came through business organizations commitment to provide a product or service with unique characteristics and features to differentiate it from the rest of other competing organizations, in the same specialty scope or environment that organization reside in, which perhaps push the organization's ambitious to excel internationally, it's a legal goal, but need features, potentials, and stunning job, where quality reside in the fact that organization provide the product or service which satisfy the client desire who seeks to obtain the best performance, and therefore gain customer satisfaction and the acceptance of product or service. The consequent of that expansion of the organization's market share and increase its reputation, where any increase in numbers of customer as a result of customer demand for product or service, it will reflect on and generate increase in sales and revenues, and therefore lead to profits increase and high return on capital (Alwan, 2009, p. 30-32), and quality achieve very important objectives and leadership for institutions, and this importance showed in the following points:

1. Company reputation: the company derives its glory and recognition from the quality of its products, and this show through the relationships that connect the institution with suppliers and employees, and their experiences and skills, and also try to offer products that meet the wishes and needs of customers in the institution.
2. Legal responsibility of quality: There is continuous increase in the number of courts that hear and rule on cases of companies which design products and presented it poorly in terms of production and distribution, and whenever this happens and depending on the type of service or industrial activity, each company will be responsible for any damage to the customer, as a result of using the product.
3. Global competition: the developments that happen on all economic and political levels largely impact the way and time of products exchange, where quality gain distinctive importance in a competitive international market, and institution and society both seek to achieve it, in order to attain the global competition and improve the economy in general.
4. Consumer protection: quality implemented in the institution activities, where specific standards and specifications will be formulated to help consumer and protect them from the commercial fraud and strengthen their confidence in the institution products, and due to quality decrease or lack of quality specifications, consumer protection groups were established to guide the customer to the best products, and the largest quality and security.
5. Costs and market share: the implementation of required quality for all processes and stages of production would provide the opportunity to discover errors, avoid carrying an extra cost, and take advantage of reducing the idle time on production, therefore reduce costs and increase profits. Paying attention to quality is the basic measure which firm could through it identify it's opinion level in comparison with the other firms, and also give firm the ability to achieve sustainable success (success after success), and not just staying within the competitive framework, and work to document and prepare many effective programs and mechanisms to discover the problems and try to find the ideal solutions for it, and

also search for the potential problems that may arise in the future, which could negatively have impact on the product or service, and expected results.

6. As we know, top management has the main responsibility for implementing TQM system of the firm, who by virtue of authority is responsible for staffs, suppliers, and customers, and it's also responsible for the success of firm that it manages, but it's understood that the important things in implementing this quality programs that it's the responsibility of employees and workers, as a whole at all levels, and it isn't just a task of senior management or quality programs coordinator, therefore motivating and encouraging employees to train at all levels and phases in the various disciplines on the fundamentals and concepts of quality consider one of the most important steps that help senior management to determine the appropriate procedures for continuous quality improvement.

9.3 Field study procedures:

The researcher in this section identify used study methodology, study population, and study sample, as well as a description for the user study tool, preparation steps, and method used to ensure the sincerity and constancy of the tool, and finally the statistical methods used.

9.3.1 Study methodology:

In light of the study problem and its questions, the appropriate approach for the current study is descriptive method, which based on the study of phenomenon as it actually exists, cares about describing it accurately, and expressing it qualitatively or quantitatively, where the qualitative expression describes to us the phenomenon and show its characteristics, while the quantitative expression give us a numeric description of the size of the phenomenon or its amount. This approach also isn't limited to data collection and distribution, but it moves beyond that because it includes some interpretation of these data.

1. Study population and study sample: Male and female workers and employees of Al Rajhi Bank. After making sure that questionnaire holds a high degree of validity, reliability, sincerity, and constancy, the implementation was done on the final sample, which consists of (124) males and (27) females, from the total number of the study population. A description of the study sample, according to the primary variables shows below:

Sex:

Table (1) sex of study sample

Sex	Frequency	%
Male	124	82.1
Female	27	17.9
Total	151	100.0

Source: field study data, 2016 It
 shows from the table (1) that (82.1%) from sample members are male, and (17.9%) are female.

2. Housing:

Table (2) housing of study sample

Housing	Frequency	%
City	146	96.7
Village	5	3.3
Total	151	100.0

Source: field study data, 2016

It shows from the table (2) that (96.7%) from sample members live in the city, and only (3.3%) live in the village.

3. Qualification:

Table (3) qualification of the study sample

Qualification	Frequency	%
Secondary school	26	17.3
Diploma	32	21.2
Bachelor	83	55.0
Master	10	6.6
Total	151	100.0

Source: field study data, 2016

It shows from the table (3) that (55.0%) from sample members carry bachelor degree, (21.2%) hold a diploma, (17.3%) hold the secondary certificate, and only (6.6%) are master holders.

9.3.3 Study tool:

Researcher used questionnaire as a tool for the current study, and after defining the objectives of questionnaire to identify the impact of implementing basic services quality on Al Rajhi bank profitability, and also implementing it on the supplementary services, the researcher accessed the educational periodicals and journals, and the previous researches and studies relevant to the current study problem, and also interviewed a number of specialists in this field to benefit from their expertise in designing the questionnaire. The researcher formulated the questionnaire's paragraphs and distributed on the dimensions based on this research literatures review, and before actually start to implement the questionnaire on the study sample, the researcher first made sure that questionnaire is valid for implementation, by testing the consistency and sincerity of the tools; as follows

First: Arbitrators sincerity

The Study tool sincerity was verified by presenting it to a group of specialists and experience arbitrators as an academic and faculty members, and addressed a letter to them that explain the problem, objectives, and questions of the study. The (5) arbitrators, as shown in the appendix (2) were asked to verify the degree of paragraphs propriety and clarity, the degree of belonging to the dimension, integrity of language format, and also examining the response categories and its appropriateness level. Based on the arbitrators' opinions about the appropriateness level of the tool with the study objectives, some sentences were modified linguistically, and others were added or deleted according to their guidance and suggestions, bringing the number of sentences in the questionnaire to (15) paragraphs spread over two dimensions. As a result, it's safe to say that study tool enjoy the arbitrator's consistency and sincerity

Second: internal consistency sincerity

The questionnaire sincerity was verified by the internal consistency method, which gives an indication about the consistency level between paragraphs within the same dimension, and the consistency level of these paragraphs with the dimension that belongs to. Availability of the internal consistency sincerity was verified by calculating Pearson correlation coefficient between the degree of each paragraph and the overall degree

of the dimension that paragraph belongs to, by implementing it on an exploratory sample that consist of (25) members.

10.3.3 Table (4) internal consistency coefficients of study tool sincerity (n = 25)

First dimension		Second dimension	
paragraph	Coefficient	paragraph	Coefficient
1	0.997*	4	0.700**
2	0.995*	5	0.211**
3	0.900*	6	0.277**
		7	0.701**
		8	0.691**
		9	0.722**
		10	0.269**
		11	0.750**
		12	0.652**
		13	0.696**
		14	0.637**
		15	0.688**

Source: field study data, 2016

As shown above, all values of correlation coefficients are positive, high, and statistically significant at a level lower than (0.05), which indicate a structural sincerity between the dimensions and each other, and between the dimensions and the overall degree of the questionnaire, and therefore the questionnaire enjoys a high degree of structural sincerity. **Third: study tool consistency**

The questionnaire consistency was verified by Cronbach Alpha coefficient method, through implementing it on an exploratory sample that consist of (25) members and the results were as follows:

Table (5) Cronbach alpha coefficients for the study tool consistency

Dimension	Cronbach alpha value
First	0.745
Second	0.800
Overall degree	0.754

Source: field study data, 2016

Cronbach alpha coefficients values ranged from (0.94) to (0.97), these values are high, and indicate that study tool enjoys a high degree of reliability and consistency.

The two researchers, see from all the past results that questionnaire; as the study tool enjoy a high degree of psychometric properties (consistency & sincerity), and therefore the possibility of implementing the questionnaire on the study final sample, and trust the accomplished results, as in the form shown in the final questionnaire, which consist of the following two parts:

First part: contain the initial data (sex, place of residence, qualification).
 Second part: consist of (15) expressions that were distributed on the following two dimensions:
 First dimension: basic services which include (3) paragraphs.

Second dimension: complementary services which include (12) paragraphs.

9.3.4 Study tool correctio

Fifth Likert scale and descriptive analysis of responses was used to correct the study sample responses, where the degree from (5) to less than (4) was given to the response (Strongly agree), the degree (4) to less than (4.21) given to the response (Agree), the degree (3) to less than (3.41) given to the response (neutral), the degree (2) to less than (2.61) was given to the response (Disagree), and the degree (1) to less than (1.81) for the response (Strongly disagree), and according to the fifth Likert scale, the following criterion was used to judge the degree of response to the expressions:-
 Responsiveness level to the expression = highest degree – lowest degree = 5-1 = 4
 Length of category = responsiveness level/number of responsiveness categories = 4/8 = 0.80

Table (6) standard for practice degree of study sample members

Arithmetic mean	Responsiveness degree
From 5- 4.21	Strongly agree
From 3.41- less than 4.21	Agree
From 2.61- less than 3.41	Neutral
From 1.81- less than 2.61	Disagree
From 1- less than 1.81	Strongly disagree

Source: field study data, 2016

9.3.5 Statistical methods:

In order to answer the study questions, the following statistical methods were used Frequencies and percentages to describe the study sample, in regard to the initial data. - Arithmetic means and standard deviation to calculate the values that were given by the study sample members for each paragraph or group of paragraphs (Dimension). - T-test to compare between the arithmetic means of study sample responses.

9.4 Discuss questions and hypotheses of the study:

9.4.1 Study questions:

First question: What is the impact of implementing total quality on the profitability of Saudi banking market?

Table (7) Means and STDEV for implementing total quality on the profitability of banking market at Al Rajhi Bank

Number	Paragraphs	Mean	STDEV	Degree
7	Keeping promises increase banking institution reputation	4.755	0.431	Very high
11	Electronic side increases client desire to purchase banking service	4.682	0.467	Very high
12	Good customers treatment increase the period they deal with the bank	4.470	0.500	Very high
14	Service availability for 24 hours straight is the reason for customers increase at the bank	4.470	0.500	Very high
1	Operational efficiencies increase daily profits at a banking institution	4.457	0.499	Very high
2	Operational efficiencies increase monthly profits level at the bank	4.450	0.499	Very high
15	Increase number of services is the main reason for customers increase at the bank	4.238	0.427	High
6	Employees credibility increase the close relationships with customers	4.197	0.503	High
8	The good treatment increase the attraction of potential consumers	4.039	0.195	High
13	Service fairness between clients raise their loyalty level to the institution	4.039	0.195	High
10	Information available at the bank increase its market share	4.033	1.185	High
3	Individuals' skills increase the annual profits of a banking institution	4.000	0.000	High
4	Training programs raise the level of customers satisfaction at the bank	4.000	0.000	High
5	Bank's employee's credibility lead to customer easiness of banking	3.986	0.199	High
9	Hospitality service inside the bank increase customer happiness	3.953	0.240	High
Dimension general mean		4.252	0.114	High

Source: field study data, 2016

It notices from the table (7) above that impact of implementing total quality on the profitability of Al Rajhi Saudi banking market came at a high degree, with an arithmetic mean of (4.252), and the sequences of paragraphs, according to its mean strength as follows:

1. Keeping promises increase banking institution reputation.
2. Electronic side increases client desire to purchase banking service.
3. Good customers' treatment increase the period they deal with the bank.
4. Service availability for 24 hours straight is the reason for customers increases at the bank.
5. Operational efficiencies increase daily profits at a banking institution.
6. Operational efficiencies increase monthly profits level at the bank.
7. Increase number of services is the main reason for customers increases at the bank.
8. Employees' credibility increases the close relationships with customers.
9. The good treatment increases the attraction of potential consumers.
10. Service fairness between clients raises their loyalty level to the institution.
11. Information available at the bank increases its market share.
12. Individuals' skills increase the annual profits of the banking institution.
13. Training programs raise the level of customers' satisfaction at the bank.
14. Bank's employees' credibility leads to customer acceptance of the bank.
15. Hospitality service inside the bank increase customer happiness.

Second question: Are there any statistically significant differences from the standpoint of study sample due to the variables (sex, qualifications)?- According to sex variable

Table (8) the difference in arithmetic means of the study dimension, due to sex variable

Dimension	Sex	Quantity	Mean	STDEV	T-value	F	Sig
Primary services	Male	124	4.2231	0.31443	-7.311	149	0.000
	Female	27	4.6667	0.00000			
Supplementary services	Male	124	4.2392	0.08160	0.099	149	0.921
	Female	27	4.2377	0.03800			
Overall dimension	Male	124	4.2312	0.18989	-6.025	149	0.000
	Female	27	4.4522	0.01900			

Source: field study data, 2016

It notice from table (8) above, there are statistically significant differences in the dimension primary services, due to the sex variable with a T-value of (7.311), which is significant at level (0.000), and in favor of females, while there were no statistically significant differences in the dimension of supplementary services, due to the sex variable with a T-value of only (0.099), which is significant at level (0.921), but in regard to overall dimension, it notice there are statistically significant differences, due to the sex variable with a T-value of (6.025), which is significant at level (0.000), and in favor of females.

- According to qualification variable:

Table (9) the difference in arithmetic means of the study dimension, due to the qualification variable

Dimension		SST	F	SSA	F	Sig
Primary services	Between group	0.512	4	0.128	1.167	0.328
	Inside group	16.011	146	0.110		
	Total	16.522	150			
Supplementary services	Between group	0.012	4	0.003	0.531	0.713
	Inside group	0.844	146	0.006		
	Total	0.857	150			
Overall dimension	Between group	0.115	4	0.029	0.775	0.543
	Inside group	5.412	146	0.037		
	Total	5.527	150			

Source: field study data, 2016

Table (9) above, shows no statistically significant differences in the fields of dimension, and also dimension total.

9.4.2 Hypotheses discussion:

1. There is no statistically significant impact of implementing quality on the tangible earnings at Al Rajhi Bank.
2. There is no statistically significant impact of implementing quality on the intangible earnings at Al Rajhi Bank.

Table (10)

impact of implementing quality on tangible earnings at Al Rajhi bank/ One-Sample Statistics

	Quantity	Mean	STDEV
Primary services	151	4.302	0.332
Supplementary services	151	4.390	0.075

Source: field study data, 2016

Table (11) impact of implementing quality on intangible earnings at Al Rajhi bank/ One-Sample Statistics

	T-value	F	Sig	Mean difference
Primary services	48.223	150	0.000	1.302
Supplementary services	201.466	150	0.000	1.238

Source: field study data, 2016

There are statistically significant impact of implementing quality on the tangible earnings at Al Rajhi bank, where the T-value amount to (48.223), and its significant at the level (0.000), and there are also statistically

significant impact of implementing quality on the intangible earnings at Al Rajhi bank, where the T-value amount to (201.466), and its significance at the level (0.000), which indicate that total quality implementation has an impact on the profitability of the Saudi banking market (Al Rajhi bank).

10. Result & recommendations

10.1 Study results:

The study arrived at the following results:

1. There are statistically significant impacts of implementing total quality on the tangible earnings at Al Rajhi Bank.
2. There are statistically significant impacts of implementing total quality on the intangible earnings at Al Rajhi Bank.
3. There is a statistically significant relationship between the quality of actual banking service provider and the customer satisfaction.
4. There is a statistically significant relationship between the satisfaction and customer loyalty of Al Rajhi Bank.

10.2 Recommendation:

The study arrived at the following recommendations:

1. The need of Al Rajhi bank to design special strategies and policies to actually improve the quality of banking services, through developing and improving the tangible and physical aspects, and showing the interest and personal knowledge of customers.
2. The need of Al Rajhi bank management to control the performance of its staffs, and conduct purposeful training courses to improve their performance, the speed of achievement, good treatment of customers, and accustom them always to smile.
3. Pay attention to customers' complaints and suggestions, and respond to them as soon as possible. Otherwise, the bank will lose a lot of customers.
4. Conduct attractive marketing offers for the current customers, and not to the one from outside the Al Rajhi Bank.
5. Provide the physical and moral incentives for employees with highest achievement and least revolt from customers.
6. Set goals for employees to fulfill the customer's request in less than ten minutes.
7. Advice bank management to raise the credibility of their employees and to stay away from some of the phrases that lessen bank reputation, such as you won a credit card.
8. Make it easy for customers' families to open accounts to gain their loyalty and increase the profitability.
9. The need to perform continuous annual researchers to study the quality level of banking services, customer's satisfaction, and their loyalty degree to connect it with profitability.

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